

MALE VOCALIZATIONS OF THE WEDDELL SEAL (*LEPTONYCHOTES WEDDELLII*) AND LEOPARD SEAL (*HYDRURGA LEPTONYX*) IN THE WEST ANTARCTIC PENINSULA WATERS

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The acoustic behaviour of the Weddell seal (*Leptonychotes weddellii* (Lesson, 1826)) and leopard seal (*Hydrurga leptonyx* (Blainville, 1820)) in the waters off the West Antarctic Peninsula is relatively understudied. Gaining insights into their patterns and drawing comparisons with other regions will enhance our understanding of the behavioral ecology of both species. From August 2021 to February 2022, we carried out continuous and opportunistic acoustic recordings in the waters of the Wilhelm Archipelago using SoundTrap 300 HF and SoundTrap 600 HF (Ocean Instruments) acoustic recorders. This recording time frame allowed us to cover the reproductive periods of both species when they are most acoustically active. The recordings were analysed using the Cornell Lab Raven Pro v1.6.5 software, CRAN packages, and R-based tools. We analysed 56 hours of high-quality seal recordings. Only male sounds were utilised and categorised. We identified four main acoustic signals of male leopard seals: high double trill, low double trill, low single trill, and hoot with low single trill. Male Weddell seals have been identified to produce various trills, whistles, pulses, chirps, and tones in their vocalizations, including those found within the ultrasonic spectrum. The duration of each call, along with its amplitude, frequency range, occurrence rates, and sequence were assessed. Our results provide the first detailed descriptions of the male calls produced by both species in the waters of the Wilhelm Archipelago. Further recordings are necessary to give a complete overview of their vocal repertoires for future comparisons with other regions and to enhance our understanding of seal species' population structure and reproductive ecology.